

WORLD
ANTHROPOLOGICAL
UNION
CONGRESS

Antigua, Guatemala
November 3-8, 2025

IUAES
International UNION of
ANTHROPOLOGICAL and
ETHNOLOGICAL sciences

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JOINT STATEMENT: Upholding Integrity and Collaboration for the WAW 2025 Congress August 15, 2025

This is a joint statement of the [WAW Steering Committee](#) and the [WAW Congress Organising Committee](#) for the Guatemala Congress.

When the WAW Steering Committee approved the proposal for a Congress in Antigua, Guatemala, the event was enthusiastically regarded as an opportunity to put the spotlight on the region and help bring together anthropologists from across the globe. Ricardo A. Fagoaga Hernández agreed to spearhead this organizing effort, and this agreement was formalized in the March 2025 Memorandum of Understanding (MOU), signed by Mr. Fagoaga and WAW Steering Committee co-chairs Gordon Mathews (representing WCAA) and Isaac Nyamongo (representing IUAES). This MOU provides a clear framework for organising the Congress, establishing the authority of the Organising Committee to manage all aspects of the Congress, including content, programming, and disciplinary matters, and reflecting WAW leadership's binding commitment to respect and support that mandate. Importantly, all participants are asked at registration to acknowledge and abide by the MOU's provisions on professional conduct, anti-harassment, and inclusion. Organising a global Congress is a complex undertaking, with many stakeholders among whom disagreements over organisational decisions are bound to arise.

Over the past several months, one set of interferences from individual members that are also part of constituent parts (such as the Council of Commissions) of IUAES, one of WAW's branch organisations, particularly regarding panel acceptance/rejection decisions, persisted and, indeed, escalated without any formal intervention on the part of the WAW Steering Committee, despite multiple requests for such intervention. Throughout its operations, the Organising Committee has been consistently guided by the established MOU and its clear rules, ensuring transparent and accountable governance. Any portrayal of these actions as authoritarian or as motivated by personal bias constitutes a misrepresentation of the procedural framework and the diligent efforts to uphold the integrity of the Congress for the entire global anthropological community.

The elected WAW leadership recognises that recent conflicts have placed unnecessary strain on Congress preparations, and that delays in addressing serious and repeated complaints regarding inappropriate interventions by individual members that are also part of constituent parts (the IUAES Council of Commissions) of IUAES, one of the branch organisations of WAW, created a situation in which the Organising Committee felt obligated to take measures to safeguard the Congress's integrity and the trust of its participants.

In the spirit of moving forward constructively and in good faith, the Organising Committee has agreed to reinstate to full Congress participation the individuals whose participation it

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had revoked. WAW leadership, in turn, commits to dealing with their past actions and formally addressing concerns regarding their conduct, particularly actions that sought to undermine the authority of the Organising and Scientific Committees.

To prevent similar issues in the future and to strengthen governance, WAW leadership and the Organising Committee will jointly establish an independent oversight committee. This body will address disputes related to Congress governance, adherence to ethical principles, and unauthorized interventions, as articulated within the MOU, as well as responsible professional conduct more generally. It will operate as a binding mechanism under both the MOU and WAW's constitutional obligations, without diminishing the Organising Committee's existing authority.

WAW leadership invites the Brazilian Anthropological Association (ABA), Asociación Latinoamericana de Antropología (ALA), and Colegio de Etnólogos y Antropólogos Sociales (CEAS) to review or amend their recent public statements regarding the Congress, as certain claims do not accurately reflect the Organizing Committee's leadership or activities.

To foster a clear and effective working relationship, both parties affirm their understanding of the established governance structure. The Chair of the Organising Committee will serve as an ex-officio WAW Steering Committee member while working on the Congress, as provided in WAW's Operational Guidelines and Rules (OGRs).

Both parties affirm that the WAW 2025 Congress will proceed as planned in Antigua, Guatemala, from 3–8 November 2025. WAW leadership and the Organising Committee commit to full cooperation in delivering a successful and inclusive event for the global anthropological community.

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WAW 2025 Congress

